

DiRAC Facilities utilization & energy report

¹In the era of high-performance computing, supercomputer clusters have become indispensable tools for tackling complex scientific, engineering, and data-intensive challenges. However, the effective utilization of these computational powerhouses is a dual imperative - maximizing their usage rate while minimizing their environmental footprint. This report delves into the optimization of supercomputer clusters with a dual focus: enhancing usage efficiency to extract the utmost value from these resources and implementing energy-saving measures to reduce the environmental impact and operational costs. As technology advances and computational demands grow, the synergy of efficient usage and sustainable operation is paramount in ensuring the continued relevance and accessibility of supercomputer clusters.

Part 1. Quota Allocation and Queuing System

¹Quota allocation and queuing systems play a pivotal role in governing how users employ the computational resources. Quotas determine the amount of computational power and time allocated to individual projects, preventing resource monopolization, and ensuring fair access. Meanwhile, the queuing system acts as a traffic controller, optimizing the use of cluster resources by managing the sequence and distribution of computational tasks. Users submit their jobs to designated queues, and the queuing system assigns priority and execution order based on factors such as job size, time constraints, and available resources. An effective quota and queuing system not only promotes fair resource allocation but also contributes to increased usage rates, as it enables users to submit jobs confidently and ensures efficient scheduling, ultimately maximizing the cluster's capabilities.

¹The primary objective of this part is to enhance the efficiency of CPU quota time allocation for research projects. In order to achieve this, a comprehensive analysis was conducted utilizing the historical usage data of the DiRAC facilities. The investigation delved into the usage patterns of users in each quarter, aiming to evaluate the effectiveness of the current quota allocation. By comparing the historical allocation with the users' actual usage, insightful suggestions can be made for future CPU time allocation. Additionally, based on the observed behaviour of users, predictions can be made to anticipate their future requirements and adapt the allocation accordingly. Lastly, we assess the impact of large project reservations on the queuing system.

Overview of DiRAC historical usage data

¹ These paragraphs are completed with the help of AI.

DiRAC facilities usage data were downloaded from <https://safe.epcc.ed.ac.uk/dirac>. It reports usage & quota by project, machine, user, and time. Time Granularity is up to 1 day. In DiRAC facilities, quota time is allotted to projects on a quarterly basis, specifically on the 1st of January, April, July, and October. Any unused quota time does not carry over to the next quarter. If a project or user exhausts their allocated quota before the end of the quarter, they are restricted from submitting further jobs to the regular queue, even in cases when the supercomputer has available resources. Therefore, all analysis is conducted based on projects and quarters, utilizing data from 1/1/2018, onwards. Our primary emphasis is on the facilities in Leicester, Cambridge, Durham, and Edinburgh.

Figure 1

Figure 1 shows the number of projects in each facility. 10 facilities have 20 or more projects and 6 have less than 10 projects. Most facilities we are focused on have a large enough number of projects.

Figure 2

Figure 2 shows number of users per project in each facility. The median number of project members is less than 5 in all facilities except one. More than 75% projects have fewer than 8 members. Nearly half of the projects have only 3 or fewer members. As quota is allocated to project, forecasting the behaviour of projects with a limited number of members may pose challenges, given the significant variations in individual user work patterns.

Utilization of Quota time

We have historical core hour availability data of Cambridge, Leicester, Durham, and Edinburgh machines since Q2 2019. In Figure 3, the bar height shows the available CPU hours in each quarter, red line represents the ratio of total allocated quota hour to CPU hours (unity for a fully allocated system) and the green line is the ratio of total used hours to available core hours. A few projects had allocated quota time above the DiRAC portion of the system, which explains occasional total rates exceeding unity (for example the dp004 project receives additional non-DiRAC time due to the hosting share of the relevant systems).

Figure 3 : Showing usage statistics as a function of time for different DiRAC systems. The blue bars represent the total core hours (left axis), the red lines show the fraction of the DiRAC time used (right axis), and the green lines show the fraction of the system allocated to DiRAC projects (right axis).

Generally, the utilization rate (red line) is consistently lower than the allocated quota rate (green line), implying that projects are able to use more of the system than they are allocated. In most quarters, the facilities are not operating at full capacity. However, it is noteworthy that the gap between the quota rate and utilization rate is more pronounced in the Edinburgh facility (Tesseract) compared to Leicester, Cambridge, and Durham. This discrepancy arises from the fact that the latter facilities permit users to submit jobs to lower-priority queues once they've exhausted their project quotas. In essence, more active projects can make use of the CPU time left unused by less active projects. It also explains why the utilized hours sometimes exceed the allocated hours. **The introduction of lower-priority queues has a beneficial impact on enhancing the overall utilization of DiRAC facilities.**

Analysis of per-quarter usage patterns

As we discussed in last section, not all projects use up their allocated quota within each quarter. In addition to the utilization of low-priority queue, it is proposed to adjust quota allocations by providing 'busy' projects with more quota time and 'lazy' projects with reduced quota time, in order to improve system utilization. This will involve transferring core hours away from projects unlikely to use them (within a given quarter) to projects who can make use of them, and who would otherwise be running in low priority queues at the end of each quarter (with inefficiencies increased by reduced queue run times).

To achieve this, taking a quarter as statistical period, we collected the weekly quota usage ratio for every project. By comparing cumulative weekly usage pattern in every project quarter, we aimed to identify projects that exhibited faster usage rates and quantify the extent of their speed at using up their quota. To classify projects based on their usage behaviour, we divided them into two groups: "busy" projects, which were defined as those utilizing more than 95% of their quota by the end of the quarter, and "lazy" projects, which did not reach this threshold.

Figure 4

Figure 4 show the comparison of usage curves between busy and lazy project quarters. To ensure the reliability of our findings and eliminate the influence of smaller projects, we focused on projects with a quota allocation of more than 3% of total quota time available for that quarter. These selection criteria allowed us to conduct a robust analysis and gain valuable insights into the utilization patterns of big projects. There is a clear departure between the usage pattern of busy and lazy projects. The solid lines are the median usage rate of each quarter. At middle of each quarter, i.e., roughly week 7, more than half of the busy projects had used up more than 50% of their quota (see blue solid line). Meanwhile, very few lazy projects used more than 50% (see orange shaded area) at week 7.

Utilizing 95% of the allocated quota time serves as a reliable criterion for identifying busy projects. Consequently, it is a sound strategy to allocate these busy projects with more quota time in the subsequent quarter. Furthermore, an intriguing observation is that if a project consumes over 50% of its quota by week 7, it is very probable that the project will deplete its quota by the end of this quarter. **Introducing a dynamic mechanism to allocate more time to these busy projects at the middle of each quarter would further enhance the overall utilization of DiRAC facilities.** However, exceptions should be made in cases where there are good reasons preventing adequate usage of the system, for example extended maintenance periods in the first have of a quarter or large reservations in place preventing other

projects from using their quota. In these situations, the decision week could be delayed by a period equal to the length of the disturbance.

Impact on the queueing system by large scheduler reservations.

At times, the DiRAC systems can allocate a specific number of nodes exclusively for designated projects over a defined period, primarily to allow large jobs (spanning more than 50% of the system) to run efficiently, enabling job restarts to occur without significant resource being wasted while other nodes drain. This reservation policy enables larger projects to bypass the queue, ensuring their timely completion. However, this may lead to potentially extended queue times for jobs from other projects, as the number of available nodes is reduced during this period. The capability systems in particular are more likely to involve large reservations. For example, COSMA8 had a 516-node reservation (out of 528 nodes) in place in June 2023.

Figure 5

We investigate this issue by delving into a specific case on the Durham COSMA8 machine. Figure 5 displays the average job pending time (i.e. how long a job is queueing for) of COSMA8 from February 2023 to July 2023. The blue line represents the daily average job pending time in minutes, excluding those jobs executed on reserved nodes. The two substantial reservation periods are highlighted in red shading. It is evident that, during these reservation periods, the average pending time for both multi-node jobs (indicated by the red dashed line) and all jobs (denoted by the red solid line) is notably longer compared to regular periods (as indicated by the green dashed and solid lines). This outcome aligns with our expectations. **Allowing other projects to make use of alternative machines during reservation periods offers the possibility of significant advantages**, particularly for projects who use their allocation in a consistent linear manner (and cannot easily make up for lost time by running more jobs simultaneously at a later date).

Summary

Here are some suggestions for improving DiRAC facility utilization:

- Allowing projects that have used up their quota to submit jobs to a low-priority queue can significantly improve overall utilization.
- Allocate more quota time in the next quarter to the projects which used more than 95% of quota time this quarter.
- Projects which used more than half of their quota at week 7 of each quarter are very likely to be 'busy' projects. They usually need more computing time than their allocated quota. Introducing a dynamic mechanism to allocate more time to these busy projects at the middle of each quarter would be helpful, at the expense of project identified as unlikely to use their full quota.
- Offer the users the access to other facilities when there is a big reservation. This could be time taken away from projects who have underused their allocation during the previous quarter.

Part 2. Energy consumption

The energy consumption of supercomputers can be divided into two distinct but intertwined components. The first component, which is often in the spotlight, is the machine usage. It relies on the complex interplay between the efficiency of computer chips in managing energy and the optimization of software code. Maximizing the computational power while minimizing energy wastage is at the core of this aspect. Code efficiency, parallel processing, and optimizing algorithms all play a crucial role in achieving this delicate equilibrium. However, the second component, the cooling system often escapes our immediate attention. Yet, it is a vital and easily underestimated part of the energy consumption. The cooling system ensures that the supercomputer operates within safe temperature ranges and remains reliable. As supercomputers generate immense heat during their operations, the energy consumed for cooling is substantial. Balancing these two aspects, machine usage and the cooling system, is essential for achieving both peak performance and energy efficiency in supercomputer clusters. The power utilisation effectiveness (PUE) is used to define the ratio of total power to that used by compute.

In this part of the study, our primary focus is on the energy consumption of the cooling system. We analyse this using historical energy data from the DiRAC COSMA facility at Durham University. Employing machine learning algorithms, we delve into the connection between energy consumption and local meteorological data, seeking insights that can inform future large-scale project planning. Additionally, we explore the idea of implementing a CPU energy cap, a measure intended to conserve energy. Finally, we introduce two tools that we've developed – one for querying user's energy consumption history and the other for identifying users whose code optimization may require improvement.

Cooling System power consumption

The cooling system transfers the heat from coolant (warm water comes out of the data centre) to outdoors (either venting it to the atmosphere, or reusing it for space heating) and is indispensable for ensuring the stable functioning of DiRAC facilities. However, cooling

comes at the cost of significant power consumption. The cooling system used by COSMA has two configurations available: one is a free air cooler, and the other is an active chiller. They operate in a cyclical manner. When the cooling demand is low, the free air cooler is active while the chiller is inactive. Conversely, when the cooling demand is high, the active chiller becomes operational, and the free air cooler is deactivated. The active chiller, when functioning at full capacity, consumes over 150kW of power, whereas the free air cooler requires less than 20kW.

We investigate the historical COSMA power usage and meteorological records over the past 3 years to try to find a way to decrease the power usage of cooling system without affecting machine performance. In Figure 6, we present five separate panels, highlighting the five datasets in September 2022 that we used in our analysis, as an example. Upon visual examination, the power consumption of the cooling system (the top two panels) exhibits a strong correlation with outdoor air temperature (the middle panel) and a relatively weaker connection with humidity and machine power consumption (the lower two panels). Here, the heat energy transferred to the coolant fluid is proportional to the machine power consumption.

Figure 6

There is a commonly occurring scenario which is interesting to consider: we have a large project to be run in the next few weeks, and we know the future temperature and humidity

from the weather forecast. For the purpose of saving energy, when should we schedule these jobs to be run in COSMA without affecting the performance? This is a classic time series challenge where we applied a Long Short-Term Memory (LSTM) network, a type of recurrent neural network (RNN). We utilized air temperature, humidity, and machine power consumption as input variables to train the LSTM network for predicting chiller system power consumption.

Our dataset consists of COSMA power consumption meteorological records spanning from 6 February 2020 to 30 September 2023. We've structured the data in half-hour intervals. The initial 90% of the dataset, covering the period from 6 February 2020 to 15 May 2023, is allocated for training purposes, while the remaining 10%, which extends from 16 May 2023 to 30 September 2023, is used for testing. We employ a seven-day sequence to forecast the subsequent seven-day energy usage. Variables such as temperature, humidity, and COSMA machine power consumption, both individually and in combination, serve as inputs for our prediction model.

In Figure 7, we observe a comparative analysis between the LSTM model's forecasts and the actual data of cooler's power consumption. The predictive accuracy is noticeably higher when temperature data is utilized as the input as opposed to the models that use humidity and power consumption data. Particularly, the predictive capability of the model for free air cooler energy usage is notably poor when using either humidity or machinery power consumption as input variables. This observation is consistent with our preliminary assessments conducted through visual analysis.

Figure 7

To quantify the performance of our LSTM network across different inputs, we rely on the test loss as the key indicator of predictive accuracy. Test loss, specifically, is a measure of the discrepancy between the model's predictions and the actual observed values during the test period. A lower value of test loss signifies a model that predicts more accurately and thus has a higher performance. Figure 8 illustrates that test loss versus epoch represents the change in the model's prediction error as it undergoes successive training cycles. Each epoch on the horizontal axis signifies a complete pass through the entire training dataset, while the test loss on the vertical axis measures the model's accuracy on the unseen test dataset. The models reach a point of stability post epoch 1250, which is when they deliver their optimal performance. Figure 7 illustrates the performance of the model at the 2000th epoch.

Figure 8 Showing accuracy of machine learning models

In Figure 8, among these parameters, air temperature (blue solid line) exhibits the lowest loss, signifying its primary significance in influencing chiller power consumption. In contrast, humidity (orange) and machine power consumption (green) have substantially higher losses. Incorporating humidity and machine power consumption alongside air temperature does not significantly enhance the predictions. This result is both surprising and aligns with our initial hypotheses, emphasizing the critical role of air temperature as the primary factor affecting cooling system power consumption, if not the sole factor. In contrast, machine power appears to exert a significantly lesser influence, possibly due to the relatively minor variation in coolant temperature when compared to outdoor air temperature fluctuations. Therefore, as a first order approximation we can use external temperature to predict cooling demand. **Ideally, arranging power intensive jobs to run at cold time (e.g., at night or in winter months) would reduce the power consumption of cooling system.**

In Figure 6, a distinct boundary emerges on 14 September 2022 (dashed orange line). Prior to this date, the free air cooler power exhibits a negative correlation with air temperature; the chiller is fully working when free air cooler is off. After this date the free air cooler power has a positive correlation with air temperature; chiller power is much less. This is a result of the temperature drop in Durham after 14/09/2022, which led to reduced cooling pressure and, consequently, the free air cooler power became active for most of the time, while the chiller remained mostly inactive.

Figure 9 Showing the correlation between free-air cooler power and air temperature.

To determine the threshold temperature, we conducted an analysis by comparing the two transition periods before and after the winter of 2022. Figure 9 illustrates the daily average free air cooler power (in blue) and the daily average air temperature (in red) from July 2022 to September 2023. Within the time frame highlighted by the green shaded area, free air cooler power exhibits a positive correlation with air temperature, while outside this period, they display a negative correlation. **As a result, we can approximately identify the threshold temperature as 14°C.** The similar threshold can be found by examining the variation in air temperature and cooling system power between day and night.

In summary, the power consumption of the cooling system is primarily, if not exclusively, influenced by air temperature. When the daily temperature falls below 14°C, the utilization of an energy-efficient free air cooler suffices to cool the Durham COSMA machine. **Therefore, running large projects during the winter and nighttime represents an ideal strategy for conserving energy within the cooling system, and thus improving the overall PUE.**

Machine Power Cap

Some MPI codes experience significant synchronization overhead, particularly when nodes are engaged in polling and waiting for data rather than active computation. This inefficiency results in a substantial waste of energy.

The histogram presented in Figure 10 illustrates the energy usage distribution of jobs over the last six quarters. The x-axis represents the power consumption per node in watts, while the y-axis displays the number of jobs falling within each power consumption range. The histogram exhibits a somewhat bimodal distribution, with one peak around 300-400W and another peak above 600W. Upon investigating jobs that exceeded 600W per node, we find that

a significant portion of them were running the Gadget code, which exhibits suboptimal MPI synchronization optimization.

Figure 10

Here, we conducted a small-scale test in which we imposed power cap on COSMA8, with the assumption that these limits would not impact performance but would solely result in reduced energy consumption. Figure 11 illustrates the extent of energy savings achievable by applying power caps to COSMA8. The relationship demonstrates a relatively linear pattern, indicating that setting a power cap at 600W can yield approximately 50,000 kWh in energy savings per quarter. Notably, during quarters (e.g., 2023Q2) with very few high-power consumption jobs, the savings are considerably diminished. We note that the runtime of some

jobs will be adversely affected by a power cap, but we ignore that effect here, assuming that for multi-node jobs displaying high power consumption are spending a significant amount of time polling for MPI messages. However, due to the uncertainties around this, and the unwillingness to test a draconian power cap on a live production system, we conclude that a more effective means of conserving energy would be to optimise codes. **However, a seasonal power cap adjustment may be a good way of reducing energy consumption.**

Figure 11

Energy consumption query code

Overview:

The energy query script is a Python tool designed to display the cumulative energy consumption of a specific task or user within a defined time frame.

```
./energy.py -j 6425047
```

Input:

Job ID only, or User ID, start date, end date

Options:

Use the command-line arguments to specify the type of query:

- j Job id
- u User id, [default: current user]
- S Start date, YYYY-MM-DD [default: yesterday]
- E End date, YYYY-MM-DD [default: 14 days prior to start date]

Output:

A summary table, like

jobID,	run time,	Nnodes,	energy,	user,	project,	machine
6425047	123.422	8	248440.527746	dc-bogul	dp058	cosma7

Or

Start date,	end date,	energy,	user,	machine
2023-10-05	2023-10-19	0.000	rrtx34	COSMA7

Email alert system of low-efficiency jobs

A Python script is employed to identify jobs with runtimes exceeding one hour while exhibiting a CPU usage rate below 12%. Such jobs are most probably utilizing only a single core (or small number) within an entire node (128 cores for COSMA8). The script is designed to automatically send email notifications to the users of these low-efficiency jobs, advising them to optimize their code.